

The Effect of Mathway on Mathematics Students' Performance in Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Mathway on Mathematics students' performance in Imo State. Two research questions and two hypotheses' questions guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research designs with non-equivalent groups. The population of the study was 208 students, with a sample size of 78 students including 42 males and 36 females through purposive sampling technique. The reliability coefficient of the Students' Performance Test on Calculus was established at 0.79 using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. Data obtained from the instruments were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while ANCOVA for the hypotheses question. The result revealed that the students taught with Mathway were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method. Furthermore, there was no significant difference between male and female Mathematics students using Mathway in learning Mathematics. Based on the findings, it was recommended that: The government should incorporate Mathway software across secondary schools in Imo State to enhance teachers' variation of teaching methods. Also, teachers should be trained on the use of Mathway to enable them teach with the software's as computer assisted instructional facilities.

Keywords: Mathway, students' performance and Gender.

Introduction

Calculus is a branch of Mathematics which has a wide application in other areas such as statistics, analytical geometry, algebra and almost all disciplines, such as Physics, Engineering, Medicine, Economics, Chemistry Geography, Computer Science and information systems. It is an area of Mathematics perceived as the main source of failure among undergraduates because of its nature, which are abstract and complex ideas. Others are un-engaging teaching methods and inadequate course design, ineffective study techniques, and the classroom environment (Saha, et al., 2024; Chand, et al., 2021).

Mathematics learning tools such as Mathway, Geogebra, Photomath, Todomath, Microsoft Math and others helps develop the student's academic achievement and enhances their understanding. Also, it saves their effort and time and helps reduce the gap between students by reducing individual differences. Students who used smart device applications performed better than those students who did not use them. Therefore, the introduction of smart devices in learning and teaching may help students raise their academic achievement levels, which in turn leads to the quality of provided education (Etcuban & Pantinople, 2018; Fabian, Topping & Barron, 2018; Hadjinor, Asotigue & Pandangamun, 2021; Mhlanga, 2018). The use of smart devices and the features they contain in teaching students of different ages to impact them positively more than if they were taught using traditional methods. This is because smart devices provide interactive educational applications that attract and entice students to learn and are suitable for their different abilities. Also, the ease of interaction with this information makes students attracted to and accept the educational process. This helps to improve students' performance and raise their academic

achievement levels, which leads to the effectiveness of the teaching and learning processes (Altaf, 2019; Alyan & Al-Qasimiyah, 2019; Al-Zahrani, 2019; Demir & Akpinar, 2018; Kattayat, Josey & Asha, 2017; Klimova, 2019; Quispe, et al., 2018; Costley, 2014).

Cantonjos & Labo (2018) determined the effectiveness of math apps in improving the performance of the grade 11 students in probability and statistics at Bagahanglad National High School, San Jacinto District in the Division of Masbate-Province, school year 2019-2020. The descriptive method of research would utilize in this study. The respondents were 50 Grade 11 students who were currently taking probability and statistics subject. The study used quantitative method to describe the performance level of the grade 11 learners in Probability and Statistics subject along the four identified topics and evaluate the Math Apps being used the Data analysis, and a qualitative method was used to know the effectiveness of the Math Apps in improving the performance of Grade 11 in Probability and Statistics subject. Data were gathered through test administration and interview. A Researcher-made instrument test questions and interviews schedule were utilized as the main instruments of the study.

Barrientos (2021) examined the use of math apps and the performance of grade 8 students in Mathematics under new normal education is underpinned by the TPACK framework of Shulman's (1987,1986) in describing how teacher's understanding of educational technologies and PCK interact with one another to produce effective teaching with technology. Analysis revealed that the pedagogical design as well the features design of Math Apps resulted to a very great extent. The level of the students' performance in Mathematics resulted in a great improvement from Developing into Proficient and Advanced stages.

Undergraduate students, particularly those in STEM majors, struggle with Calculus due to its abstract nature, ineffective teaching methods, and low attitude towards learning, and consequently exhibit poor performance in the subject. This difficulty stems from Mathematical anxiety and fear of the subject matter delivery, but innovative and interactive technologies have become palliatives in promoting positive attitudes and performance in Calculus.

Statement of Problem

The use of digital tools in educational settings has altered the conditions of learning across multiple disciplines. Specifically, in the discipline of mathematics, online resources such as Mathway have developed as effective aids in improving students' grasp and application of complicated mathematical concepts. Calculus, recognized for its difficulty, is a basic course for many undergraduate programs and frequently shapes students' attitudes about mathematics as a whole. Mathway functions as a problem-solving aid, allowing students to practice and confirm their calculus solutions, potentially affecting their learning outcomes and self-efficacy. However, finding a reliable and successful approach for teaching Calculus remains a significant challenge. Therefore, this study aims to explore the efficiency of Mathway on Performance and Attitude of year one undergraduate Mathematics students in Calculus.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study.

1. What is the difference in the performance of Mathematics students using Mathway application and Lecture method?
2. What is the gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application?

Hypotheses

The understated null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 percent significance level.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Mathematics students’ using Mathway application and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. There is no significant gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application

Methodology

The population of the study comprised all 208 2022/2023 academic session students of Mathematics departments. The sample of this study includes 164 Mathematics students comprising 106 males representing 64.6% and 58 females representing 35.4% from three intact classes by purposive sampling. These instruments were Students’ Performance Test on Calculus (SPTC), The reliability coefficient was determined using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and a value of 0.79 was obtained. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard, while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 5% significant level.

Results and Discussion

Research one: What is the difference in the performance of Mathematics students using Mathway application and Lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on performance of students using Mathway application and lecture method

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Effect Size
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Mathway	78	33.94	7.64	69.31	6.56	35.37	12.05
LM	53	32.57	7.53	55.89	8.26	23.32	

Results from table 1 shows a pre-test mean score of 33.94 with a standard deviation of 7.64 and a corresponding post-test mean of 69.31 with a standard deviation of 6.56 resulting into a mean gain of 35.37 for students that used Mathway for learning Calculus while a pre-test mean of 32.57 with a standard deviation of 7.53 and a post-test mean of 55.89 with a standard deviation of 8.26 and a corresponding mean gain of 23.32 was recorded for the group that used lecture method for learning Calculus. The result revealed that the mean gain of Mathway group (M=35.37) is higher than that of the lecture method (M=23.32). The effect size of 12.05 indicates that the students taught with Mathway were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method.

Research two: What is the gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of students taught Mathway application based on gender

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
MALE	42	28.19	12.73	81.56	10.73	53.37
FEMALE	36	27.88	10.970	81.56	10.73	53.68

The results in Table 2 showed that the performance of Male students exposed to the Mathway application obtained a mean score of 81.56 while their Female counterparts had a performance means score of 81.56. Their mean gain was 53.37 for males and 53.68 for females. It is therefore revealed that the performance of Male students was the same to the performance of their Female counterparts. Therefore, male and female students performed the-same in Mathway application.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Mathematics students' using Mathway application and those taught using the Lecture method.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA on the difference in the mean performance score of Mathematics students using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	6919.552 ^a	2	3459.776	85.745	.000
Intercept	12169.912	1	12169.912	301.611	.000
Pretest	1660.948	1	1660.948	41.164	.000
Group	4697.443	1	4697.443	116.418	.000
Error	4640.219	115	40.350		
Total	484069.000	118			
Corrected Total	11559.771	117			

a R Squared = .599 (Adjusted R Squared = .592)

Table 3. above showed that there was a significant difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students' taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method ($F_{1, 115} = 116.42, p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis one was rejected at 5% significance level.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application.

Table 4.4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) in the difference in performance of male and female students taught Mathematics using Math-way application.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: posttest					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1230.890 ^a	2	615.445	7.516	.001
Intercept	49644.546	1	49644.546	606.310	.000
Pretest	581.951	1	581.951	7.107	.010
Gender	664.653	1	664.653	8.117	.006
Error	4503.386	75	81.880		
Total	403638.000	78			
Corrected Total	5734.276	77			

a. R Squared = .215 (Adjusted R Squared = .186)

The results in Table 4.4 showed that the calculated F-value for the effect of gender is **8.117** at degrees of freedom of 1 and 75. The calculated p-value of **.006** was less than the 0.05 significant level, therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning; there is no significant gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application.

Discussion of Findings

The data in table 1 revealed that Students taught with Mathway were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method. Also, table 3 revealed a significant difference in the mean performance scores of Mathematics students' using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method. This result supports with that of Ghanem and Yahya (2022) with a statistically significant difference between students that used Mathway and those that did not use Mathway in learning Mathematics. It aligns with Hadjinor, Asotigue, and Pangandamun (2021) study with significant difference between pre-test and post-test performance of students that use Mathway application for solving trigonometric problems. The result is also similar to Onaifoh and Ekwueme (2017) study who also found that there was a significant difference between the mean performances of students' taught plane geometry using GeoGebra software and problem-based learning but no significant difference was observed with respect to gender.

The data in table 2 revealed that the performance of Male students was the same to the performance of their Female counterparts. Therefore, male and female students performed the-same in Mathway application. Also, the results in table 4.4 displayed no significant gender difference of Mathematics students using Math-way application.

This finding disagreed with the that of, Simegn and Asfaw (2017) investigated the influence of attitude towards mathematics on the achievement of female students in comparison with their male counterparts, as well as the relationship between attitudes and mathematics achievement. The results, in both grade levels, unveiled that student had positive attitude towards mathematics but at medium level, however, the level of female students was less than males.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that Students taught with Mathway were favoured more that those taught with the lecture method. Also, there was no significant difference between male and female Mathematics students' using Mathway application.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following among other things that:

1. The government should incorporate Mathway software across Secondary Schools in Imo State to enhance teachers' variation of teaching methods.
2. Teachers should be trained on the use of Mathway to enable them teach with the software's as computer assisted instructional facilities.

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